

Cybersecurity Awareness In African Higher Education Institutions: A Case Study Of Sudan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 18, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: December 18, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Awareness, Africa, COVID-19; Cybersecurity Undergraduate</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14515567</p>	<p><i>The crisis caused by the rapid spread of the Coronavirus (COVID-19) has imposed a rapid and profound change in the teaching and learning methods. Consequently, most higher education institutions around the world including African higher education institutions, have moved from face to face teaching to online learning and teaching. which has made the use of the Internet by university students necessary and obligatory regardless of the risks associated with unsafe use. This prompted the researchers to investigate the cybersecurity awareness level among undergraduate students at African higher education institutions based on the case country Sudan. Using exploratory research approach, a survey was conducted on a convenience sample of 1,200 undergraduate students at six public universities in Sudan. The results show that most of the undergraduate students in Sudan higher educational institutions have low cybersecurity awareness level. Further investigation using inferential statistics reveals that male students have slightly higher levels of cybersecurity awareness than female students. Most of the participants believe that the cybersecurity should be taught in schools, they are also willing to learn about cybersecurity. In addition, the results found out that students with advanced computer skills significantly different with intermediate and basic computer skills students in practicing cybersecurity.</i></p>

Introduction

Information and communications technology (ICT) has become part of our working, social and educational environment particularly after the crisis resulting from the rapid spread of the Coronavirus. COVID-19, imposed a process of rapid and profound change that included various levels; political, economic, social, and educational levels (Huang, Liu, Tlili, Yang, & Wang, 2020.). This change was related to a group of new variables notable among them is the need imposed by the crisis for the strict and universal application of the principle of "social distancing". This is what prompted the educational community in general, and researchers in the ICT filed in particular, to think and research the implications of this crisis and its fate and the extent of its impact on the education sector.

The education sector represents one of the most prominent systems that had to deal with the repercussions of the crisis (Sintema, 2020). Imposing the application of the principle of social distancing stops Face to Face teaching and depend mainly on online teaching and learning systems (Crawford, Butler-Henderson, Rudolph, & Glowatz, 2020). However, these eLearning systems needs to be effective and safe in order to ensure the regular and continuous course of interaction between students among them and students with their teachers (Oranburg, 2020).

Most higher education institutions in different countries have worked to exploit and employ ICTs to support e-learning through various e-learning applications (Miguel, Caballé, & Xhafa, 2017). With this increasing spread of information and communication technology devices and tools, the number of users of internet network in the African countries is constantly increasing, especially among undergraduate students, and access to the internet has become easier and less expensive (ITU 2019; Statista 2019). However, a majority of internet users in general and undergraduate students in particular at African countries are not properly educated about the safe use of cyber space (Bada, Sasse, & Nurse, 2019), which exposes these students to a number of risks related to the unsafe using the internet, which can range from losing information to cyber threats (Kwaa-Aidoo & Agbeko, 2018; Kshetri, 2019). Therefore, it is extremely important that all undergraduate students understand how to use internet correctly and safely.

Significance and aim of the study

Most of the higher education institutions around the world moving towards online teaching and learning during this period of the breakout of the coronavirus, awareness of cybersecurity is more important now than ever before. This study aims to shed light on the existing level of awareness of cybersecurity among undergraduate

students and suggests further work on this social and educational problem in an attempt to develop a culture of cyber safety among undergraduate students in the African countries in general and Sudan in particular.

Research Questions

The researchers sought to address the following research questions to achieve the aims of this study:

RQ1. What are the students' attitudes towards cybersecurity awareness?

RQ2. Is there any significant difference in cybersecurity awareness level according to students' gender?

RQ3. Is there any significant difference in cybersecurity awareness level between students with different computer skills?

Theoretical Framework

What is Cyberspace?

The word Cyber is derived from Cybernetics and its Greek origin means directing and controlling (Beer2002). Norbert Wiener defined it in 1948 as "the scientific study of control and communication in the animal and the machine." (Wiener 1948). Wiener used the ancient Greek word kubernetes, which mean steersman, the man who operating the long ships rudder, to describe the principle governing or directing a machine or system, the word translated into English as cybernetes. (Beer2002).

As for cyberspace, The US National Institute of Standards and Technology defines it as "the complex environment resulting from the interaction of people, software and services on the Internet by means of technology devices and networks connected to it, which does not exist in any physical form" (Hogan & Newton. 2015). The US Department of Defence defines cyberspace as "a global domain within the information environment consisting of the interdependent network of information technology infrastructures, including the Internet, telecommunications networks, computer systems, and embedded processors and controllers." (staff 2010). Others defined cyberspace as the environment in which communication over computer networks occurs (Kissel, 2011; Canongia&Mandarino, 2012; Oxford 2014). The uses and forms of control over cyberspace or cyber sovereignty differ from one country to another depending on the priorities of these countries. Some of them are security, political, Intelligence, civil, or professional, or it may be purely information. The overall entity of cyberspace is formed by the presence of three basic components that include the technical tools used, the procedures, and the human factor of programmers and users.

What is Cybersecurity?

According to the US National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) "Cybersecurity is the ability to protect or defend the use of cyberspace from cyber-attacks" (Ross, R., et al., 2013). Cybersecurity can be defined as protecting networks, devices, electronic systems, and data from any penetration, disruption, modification or illegal entry, use or exploitation that can be done by cyber-attacks that range from business enterprises to personal devices. Network security, application security, information security, organizational security, disaster recovery, and business continuity are some of the categories that need to be protected. Network protection and application security are concerned with protecting computer networks as well as ensuring that software and hardware are free of threats and vulnerabilities. Disaster recovery is the response of an organization in the event of data loss and the effort to regain operating capability in order to continue the organization's work (CISCO, 2020; Kaspersky, 2020).

Types of cybersecurity threats

According to CISCO (2020) there are four common Types of cybersecurity threats:

Phishing: Phishing is the act of sending fake emails that look like they came from a trustworthy source. The aim is to steal confidential information such as credit card numbers and login credentials. It's the most common cyber-threat. You can protect yourself from this type of threat by dealing properly with unknown source emails, or by using a technical solution that filters malicious emails.

Malware: Malware is a type of program designed to gain unauthorized access or to harm a computer

Ransomware: Ransomware is a sort of malware. Its aim is to extort money by preventing access to files or the computer system before a ransom is paid. Paying the ransom would not ensure that the files or device will be restored.

Social engineering: Social engineering is a method utilized by attackers to steer you to expose private information. They may want to call for a financial charge or access to your personal information. To make you much more likely to click on links, download malware, or accept as true with a malicious source, social engineering may be blended with any of the threats noted above.

ICTs and Cybersecurity Trend in Africa

All countries, whether developing or developed, are affected by information and communications technologies (ICTs). The African countries are no exception, they also seek to resolve the social, economic, educational, cultural and political issues of the ICT challenges (Beda, 2019; Eltahir, 2019).

According to International Telecommunication Union (ITU) Yearbook of Statistics (2019) the African countries as a group score below world averages on internet user indicators. While the world average individuals using the Internet was around 53.6 per hundred inhabitants, in 2019 that in the African countries was about one half of this (Figure 1). However, African internet using is growing rapidly. Figure 2 provide an overall picture of the increasing number of internet users in African countries during the past fifteen years. The International Monetary Fund defined SWFs as "public investment funds or arrangements with specific economic objectives (medium or long-term), owned and controlled by governments, built from foreign exchange operations, privatization returns, public fiscal surpluses or returns. Commodity exports, and these funds apply strategies that include investments in foreign financial assets, "this definition includes revenue stabilization funds, savings funds, development finance funds and government pension funds.

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development of sovereign funds (OECD) is defined as a set of financial assets directly or indirectly managed by the government to achieve economic objectives financed either by foreign exchange reserves or by the state's exports of resources. natural or public revenue or any other resources."

The International Institute of Sovereign Wealth Funds (IIB) has defined them as government investment funds consisting of various financial assets such as stocks, bonds and other financial assets, financed by the surplus achieved in the private sector, the general budget, the balance of payments, or the surplus income from The export of goods is different from other state institutions, such as the central bank, which manages foreign reserves to achieve monetary policy objectives and differs from pension funds and economic companies. as "a financial means of the state arising from the liquidity achieved in the public sector or from the central bank's existing fiscal surplus.

Figure 1. Individuals using the Internet per 100 inhabitants in African countries as compared to world averages 2019.

Figure 2. Individuals using the Internet in African countries (in millions) 2005-2019

Because of the global nature of cybercrime, many patterns of cybercrime that we see globally also affect Africa, including violations of privacy, bullying, hacking and phishing, publishing illegal content, digital piracy, cyber extortion, identity theft, and social media scams (Marcum, & Higgins, 2019). However, because of how the internet users are increasing significantly in Africa, many of these cyber-crime trends will become particularly acute and pose a significant risk (African Union Commission, 2016).

As part of the Global Forum on Cybersecurity Experiment (GFCE) initiative, the African Union Commission (AUC) and Symantec released a report analysing cybersecurity trends and government responses in Africa. The report provides an overview of developments in cybersecurity related to cybercrime on the African continent. The report notes that due to a lack of security capabilities, the absence of appropriate legislation and insufficient awareness of cybersecurity measures, Africa can be considered a fertile environment for cyber criminals. Another issue that was raised by the report was that most of the African countries did not have clear legal provisions on cybercrime and applicable electronic evidence. The report concludes that the current state of legislation on cybercrime and electronic evidence in Africa is unsatisfactory and only 20% of the African states seemed to have the minimum legislation in force. African governments will need to develop and implement successful policy, legislation and awareness campaigns to tackle the increasing wave of cyber threats to help Africa achieve its full potential.

Previous Study

Although cybersecurity is an important problem affecting Internet users not only in African higher education institutions but also in school levels around the world, in the study of Sezer, Yilmaz, and Yilmaz (2015) on determining levels of Educator awareness in Turkish schools regarding bullying. The extent of teachers' awareness levels was measured in general, with regard to the issue of personal cybersecurity in their daily lives and the precautions that can be taken in this con-text. The researchers used the survey method by distributing questionnaires to 184 teachers in various Turkish schools. The study results showed that the teachers in the study sample group had an average level of awareness about cyberbullying in general. According to the results of the study, there are statistically significant differences between teachers' awareness levels about cyberbullying based on gender variable and frequency of internet use.

In another study by Ismailova and Muhametjanova (2016) on the level of information security awareness of students in the Kyrgyz Republic. A total of 172 students from different departments of Kyrgyz University participated in the study. The study showed that, despite the vast number of reports of computer crimes on the Internet, knowledge of cybercrime is very low among students and they are often unaware of many aspects of computer crime. The study concluded that although information technology is widely used, students should be taught topics related to the safe use of the information network to prevent them from becoming victims of cybercrime.

Kim (2014) conducted study aimed at investigating the attitudes of undergraduate and graduate students in a business college in New England toward cybersecurity awareness.

the study found that colleges' students understand the value and the need for information security awareness, but many of them are not involved in practicing it. Muniandy, Muniandy, & Samsudin (2017) study, which aimed to explore the cybersecurity behaviour in five cybersecurity aspects among higher education students in Malaysia. The study depends mainly on a questionnaire distributed to (128) undergraduate students in a private university college. The results show that cybersecurity behaviour among students was unsatisfactory in all five cybersecurity aspects.

In a study of Albarashdi (2019) entitled Facebook and electronic crime in Oman: is there a relationship? It showed that most cybercrime is linked to the use of social media, especially Facebook. The study relied on the qualitative approach, whereby statistics related to cyber-crime issued from the Centre for Information Safety at the Information Technology Authority in the Sultanate of Oman were analysed, in addition to conducting interviews with (30) in-formation security experts. The study concluded that more studies are necessary to understand the causes of the increase in cybercrime, and to develop radical solutions to address the problem in the future.

Senthilkumar&Easwaramoorthy study (2017) entitled A Survey on Cybersecurity awareness among college students in Tamil Nadu. It relied on the descriptive analytical approach, as the study used a web-based questionnaire directed to (500) college students from five different cities. The survey was looking into cybersecurity awareness of three main cyberattacks: virus attacks, phishing with emails, and threats to spread personal details. The results of the study indicated that 70% of the students are aware about the virus attacks and are using antivirus software. The study concludes that the degree of awareness among college students in Tamil Nadu are having a good level of awareness on Cybersecurity that can help them protect themselves from cyber-attacks.

As for the African countries, several studies that have concerned with the issue of awareness of teachers and school students and internet users in general about cybersecurity (Kritzinger, Bada, & Nurse, 2017; Chandarman, & Niekerk, 2017; Bada, Solms, & Agrafiotis, 2019; Kshetri 2019; Venter, Blignaut, Renaud, & Venter 2019). However, there are few studies investigate the issue of awareness of educators and students about cybersecurity in higher educational institutes.

Most of these studies show that school's students are not aware of such threats related to using of the internet and there is a need for cybersecurity awareness campaigns and education initiatives that will provide knowledge and skills to school students to safely surf online for instance, the Kritzinger, Bada, & Nurse (2017) study presented an initiative in the form of a play-based curriculum, which helps school learners to become safer online and teach learners the risks related to using the Internet. The study relied on a quantitative survey of elementary school students in South Africa to determine whether a game-based curriculum could be used to improve awareness of cyber safety. a significant statistic result from the study show that 35% of students hide their online activities from their parents and 61% of parents and teachers do not supervise their students' or children's online use.

Methodology

An exploratory research approach was used due to its ability to achieve the aims of this study. A survey was designed and distributed to undergraduate students in six public educational institutions in Sudan in first semester of the 2020-2021 academic year. The content of the survey was based on the literature review of a recent studies on cybersecurity awareness (Kansai University, 2010; Muhirwe & White, 2016; Chandarman & Niekerk, 2017; Subramaniam, 2017; Muniandy, Muniandy & Samsudin, 2017)). Three key aspects were taken into consideration when designing the questionnaire: participants' knowledge of cybersecurity, cybersecurity practice and cybersecurity education.

The survey consisted of two parts. The first part of the survey included the demographic background of the students. The second part of the survey consisted of (35) statements intended to figure out the students' attitudes towards cybersecurity awareness through investigating their knowledge, practice of cybersecurity and attitude towards cybersecurity education. Five-point Likert scale statements were used for responses to questionnaire statements.

Figure 3. Design of the study

Validity and Reliability

To test the survey tool validity copies of the survey tool were sent to four scholars specialized in methodology, network and information security, educational technology, and educational psychology. The content was adjusted according to their suggestions and comments. The reliability of the questionnaire was also verified by applying it to a pilot sample consist of (30) undergraduate students from outside the study sample. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated using the SPSS program, providing a value of (0.74) for the questionnaire, which indicating accepted level of internal consistency as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients of Reliability for The Questionnaire

Aspects	No. of Statements	Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient
Knowledge of Cybersecurity	15	0.76
Cybersecurity Practice	10	0.72

Cybersecurity Education	10	0.74
Total reliability	35	0.74

The Sample

In this study a non-probability sampling method was used where we can easy contact these students. Via convenience sampling, the researchers selected 1200 undergraduate students at six public universities located in Khartoum, the capital city of Sudan.

Two version of questionnaire was design, an online copy was created using Google form and distributed to the participants by using students' emails. The invitation email provided details about the purpose of the study and clearly stating that their responses will remain strictly anonymous. Hard copies of the questionnaire were distributed by hand. A total of 1168 valid questionnaires were returned from the 1200 distributed, the following table summarize the composition of the sample.

Table 2. Demographic Information

Institution Name		Sudan					Nile Valley University	Total
		University of Khartoum	University of Science and Technology	Al-Neelain University	Omdurman Islamic University	International University of Africa		
Gender	Male	109	113	121	101	69	142	655
	Female	112	107	111	70	52	61	513
	Below 20	97	79	87	81	66	132	542
Age	20 to 25	77	52	55	34	24	23	265
	26 to 30	35	39	41	19	16	25	175
	31 to 35	4	19	23	18	6	12	82
	36 to 40	3	23	24	9	4	8	71
	Over 40	5	8	2	10	5	3	33
Academic Status	Freshman	106	118	101	93	63	93	574
	Sophomore	48	69	64	58	35	52	326
	Junior	40	0	35	16	8	38	137
	Senior	27	33	32	4	15	20	131
Computer Skills level	Basic	70	68	78	70	50	90	426
	intermediate	122	133	129	98	53	97	632
	advanced	29	19	25	3	18	16	110
Field of Study	Art	98	63	64	46	46	59	376
	Education	69	111	112	76	45	100	513
	Science	54	46	56	49	30	44	279
Total		221	220	232	171	121	203	1168
Percent		18.92%	18.84%	19.86%	14.64%	10.36%	17.38%	100%

Results and Discussion

In order to examine and address the research questions, The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used. To investigate the differences of the responses according to the participants' gender, computing skills, T-test independent sample and an ANOVA for equality of means and Scheffe's test for multiple comparisons were employed to determine the differences of the means.

Part 1 of the questionnaire dealt with background information of the participants. In part 2 of the questionnaire a Likert scale with 5-point scale was used (Strongly Disagree = 1, Disagree = 2, Neutral = 3, Agree = 4, and Strongly Agree = 5) to find out the participants' attitudes. The participants' responses were categorized into five equal range levels through following equation: the length of category = (maximum value - minimum value) ÷ number of alternatives = $(5 - 1) \div 5 = 0.80$, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3
Distribution of Categories

Description	Score	Extent of Means
Strongly Agree	5	4.21 – 5.00
Agree	4	3.41 – 4.20
Neutral	3	2.61 – 3.40
Disagree	2	1.81 – 2.60
Strongly Disagree	1	1.00 – 1.80

RQ1. What are the students' Attitudes Towards Cybersecurity Awareness?

In Part 2 of the questionnaire the researchers sought to explore the participants' attitudes towards the cybersecurity awareness. Mean scores and standard deviations for the participants' responses to each of the questionnaire statements were calculated for each of the three aspects, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics for Participants' Responses Towards Cybersecurity Awareness

statements	N	Mean	S. Deviation	Description
Knowledge of Cybersecurity				
I know much about Internet network security measures	1168	2.16	1.203	Disagree
I think Internet is safe	1168	3.43	1.354	Agree
It's safe to shop online and use Internet banking	1168	3.45	1.300	Agree
I think I will never injure someone or be injured by someone due to Internet usage	1168	3.42	1.321	Agree
I have no problems with using a computer that did not have anti-virus software installed	1168	3.43	1.366	Agree
I know what the risks when using the internet	1168	2.17	1.143	Disagree
I Know the risk of using non-genuine software	1168	2.17	1.111	Disagree
I Know the risk of clicking on unknown email link	1168	2.23	1.116	Disagree
I think using internet with my mobile is more secure than using it with my PC	1168	3.43	1.321	Agree
. I think security measures are up to the provider, not the individual	1168	3.42	1.333	Agree
. I know what measures individuals should take for cybersecurity	1168	1.91	0.839	Disagree
. I know that cybersecurity is a priority within my institution.	1168	1.93	0.811	Disagree
. I am aware of the institution's Internet use policy	1168	1.94	0.825	Disagree
. I do pay attention to my institution material about cyber security.	1168	1.87	0.812	Disagree
. I know to whom and how to report if I face cybersecurity problems in my institution.	1168	1.88	0.858	Disagree
Total mean		2.59		Disagree
Standard deviation			1.11	
Cybersecurity Practice				
. I am using antivirus and firewall to protect my computer	1168	3.05	1.343	Neutral
. I regularly scan my computer and storage devices	1168	2.47	1.542	Disagree
. I know the strong password characteristics	1168	2.44	1.328	Disagree
. I change my passwords regularly	1168	2.70	1.135	Neutral
. I regularly backup my important files	1168	2.62	1.203	Neutral
. I understand the risk of P2P sharing files	1168	2.55	1.448	Disagree
. I ensure that sensitive data is protected on my mobile device	1168	2.64	1.117	Neutral
. I use filtering software to restrict access to harmful Internet sites	1168	2.51	1.133	Disagree
. I don't open emails from unknown senders	1168	2.68	1.025	Neutral
. I use a pop-up blocker in my Web browsers	1168	2.31	1.421	Disagree
Total mean		2.60		Disagree
Standard deviation			1.27	

statements	N	Mean	S. Deviation	Description
Cybersecurity Education				
. People ought to receive Cybersecurity education	1168	3.97	0.931	Agree
. Undergraduate students should be taught thoroughly about Cybersecurity	1168	3.51	1.091	Agree
. Cybersecurity should be taught in schools	1168	3.89	0.785	Agree
. There ought to be more opportunities for Cybersecurity training at higher education institutions	1168	3.60	1.131	Agree
. Higher education institutions should provide user-friendly teaching materials online	1168	3.51	1.081	Agree
. Individuals ought to teach themselves about Cybersecurity	1168	3.56	1.037	Agree
. I would like to be taught about Cybersecurity	1168	3.54	1.058	Agree
. These days education about Cybersecurity particularly necessary	1168	3.56	1.053	Agree
. I use educational resources to educate myself about Cybersecurity	1168	3.18	1.120	Neutral
. security education is necessary even when using a security software	1168	3.51	1.049	Agree
Total mean		3.58		Agree
Standard deviation			1.03	
Total mean for the three aspects		2.92		Neutral
Standard deviation			1.14	

The results shown in Table 4 indicate that the majority of respondents disagree with most of the statements with regard to the knowledge of cybersecurity aspect, with a total mean of 2.59. It is also evident from Table 4 that the response to statements 14 and 15 had the lowest average (1.87,1.88), which shows that the majority of students do not pay attention to their institution material about cybersecurity and do not know to whom and how to report if they face cybersecurity problems in their institution and that because they do not acquaint their institutions' Internet use policy.

As for the second aspect of the questionnaire about cybersecurity practice, the students' responses reported in table 4 indicate that the level of practicing cybersecurity among undergraduate students is very low with a total mean of (2.60) and standard deviation (1.27). It is clear that the responses to statements 25, and 18 had the lowest average (2.31,2.44), which shows that the majority of students do not know the characteristics of a good password and they do not use a pop-up blocker in their web browsers to prevent unwanted pop-ups from interfering with their browsing experience, because most of the pop-ups are ads, malware, and other unwanted windows. This result is consistent with previous studies of both (Kim, 2014; Muhirwe, & White, 2016). The results of which concluded that cybersecurity awareness has a major impact on cybersecurity practice

The results of the students' response related to cybersecurity education presented in Table 4. reveal that all participants hold a positive opinion about cybersecurity education with a total average value of 3.58. This result confirms the importance of education in the field of cybersecurity and attention to educating students because reliance on modern technologies and the Internet will increase, especially in light of crises and disasters such as the Covid-19 pandemic, and thus the risks related to the unsafe use of Internet networks will increase.

The responses to statements 26, and 28, with the respective average values of 3.97, 3.89, show that the majority of respondents believe that people ought to receive Cybersecurity education and they are also agreed that Cybersecurity should be taught in schools. Asked if they use educational resources to educate themselves about cybersecurity (statement 34), participants hesitated to agree or disagree with it the responses were Natural. It can be supposed that this is not because they have no desire to do so, but because educational resources are not available, or if they are available, they are not enough, and this result is consistent with the report conducted by AUC (2016). That is, cybersecurity education and training centers are not available and lack of local expertise in most African states. For the other statements all the participants agree about the important of cybersecurity education.

It is clear that the total mean for the three aspects (2.92) related to the students' attitudes towards cybersecurity awareness showed a poor level of students' knowledge of cybersecurity in most of the items of the questionnaire and this result are consistent with previous studies (Ismailova and Muhametjanova. 2016; Muniandy, Muniandy, & Samsudin 2017; Chandarman & Niekerk 2017) and reveal that most undergraduate students in African countries do not have sufficient awareness about cybersecurity.

RQ2. Is there any significant difference in cybersecurity awareness level according to students' gender?

Independent sample T-test was employed to determine the differences of the means responses according to the gender of the sample. Table 5, shows that Levene's test for homogeneity of variances was not significant ($p=0.427 > 0.05$). It can be concluded that variances for each group were the same. The result also shows that there are significant differences between the mean value of females and males toward cybersecurity awareness level ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$), where males score higher than females as shown in table 6. This result is consistent with previous study (Venter, Blignaut, Renaud & Venter 2019).

Table 5. Independent Sample T-Test of Cybersecurity Awareness Level Between Students Gender

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		T-test for Equality of Means				
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	
Mean awareness	Equal variances assumed	.630	.427	-20.151	1166	.000	-.36529
	Equal variances not assumed			-20.085	1085.738	.000	-.36529

Table 6. Means and Standard Deviations of the Students' Responses According to Gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Female</i>	655	2.7619	.30379
<i>Male</i>	513	3.1272	.31210

RQ3. Is there any significant difference in cybersecurity practice level between students with different computer skills?

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine whether there are any statistically significant differences between students with different computer skills levels (Basic, Intermediate, and Advanced) in their cybersecurity practice level.

From Table 7 it's obvious that the mean and sample size for each computer skills level is not equal. Thus, the Levene's test has been used to examine the homogeneity of variance. The Levene's test (table 8) shows that the homogeneity of variance assumption was not met ($p = .000$). As such, the Welch's F and Brown-Forsythe's F tests were used (Table 9). The one-way ANOVA of student's average score on the measure of cybersecurity practice revealed a statistically significant main effect, Welch's $F(2, 319.212) = 85.579$, $p = 0.00 < .05$, Brown-Forsythe's $F(2, 554.244) = 77.452$, $p = 0.00 < .05$, indicating that students with different computing skills had significant different average score on the measure of cybersecurity practice level.

Games-Howell post hoc procedure was used since the homogeneity of variance assumption was not met to determine which level of the three computer skills means differed significantly. Multiple comparisons in Table 10 shows that significant differences between students' computer skills level were driven by significant differences between students with advanced computer skills and students with intermediate computer skills, the mean difference between them was .47050 ($p = 0.00$) as well as students with advanced computer skills and students with basic computer skills, the mean difference between them was .79631 ($p = 0.00$), and the mean difference between students with intermediate computer skills and students with basic computer skills was .32581 ($p = 0.00$) This indicates that there are significant differences between them on the measure of cybersecurity practice level.

Table 7. Means and Standard Deviations of the Students' Responses to Cybersecurity Practice Level According to Computer Skills Level

Computer skills level	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Basic	426	2.3446	.59853
Intermediate	632	2.6704	.75623
Advanced	110	3.1409	.59851
Total	1168	2.5959	.72608

Table 8. Test of Homogeneity of Variances

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Cybersecurity Practice level	Based on Mean	42.813	2	1165	.000
	Based on Median	39.051	2	1165	.000
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	39.051	2	1157.283	.000
	Based on trimmed mean	44.539	2	1165	.000

Table 9. One Way ANOVA Robust Tests of Equality of Means

	Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Welch	85.579	2	319.212	.000
Brown-Forsythe	77.452	2	554.244	.000

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Table 10. Games-Howell Post Hoc Test Statistics for Different Computer Skills Multiple Comparisons

(I) Skill level in using Computers	(J) Skill level in using Computers	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Basic	Intermediate	-.32581	.04178	.000	-.4239	-.2277
	Advanced	-.79631	.06401	.000	-.9477	-.6450
Intermediate	Basic	.32581	.04178	.000	.2277	.4239
	Advanced	-.47050	.06451	.000	-.6230	-.3180
Advanced	Basic	.79631	.06401	.000	.6450	.9477
	Intermediate	.47050	.06451	.000	.3180	.6230

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Conclusions

The survey was very revealing of undergraduate students' attitudes towards cybersecurity Awareness. The most important issues that emerged from the survey relate to the following:

- The majority of respondents do not have sufficient awareness about cybersecurity.
- The result shows that there are statistically significant differences between male and female students towards cybersecurity awareness in favour of male students.
- The results reveal that all the participants have a positive opinion of cybersecurity education.
- That the majority of respondents believe that the cybersecurity should be taught in schools, they are also willing to learn about cybersecurity.
- The results also indicating that students with different computing skills had significant different on the measure of cybersecurity practice level in favour of students with advanced computer skills.

Limitations

Although this study has adopted a rigorous research methodology, there are still some potential limitations that need to be addressed in future studies. First, this study deal with one country in Africa namely Sudan. Thereby, due to variations in population in African countries the generalizability of the findings of this study must be approached with caution.

This study focused and investigated higher education students' attitudes towards cybersecurity awareness. Future studies can develop a cybersecurity awareness and education framework for African countries.

Recommendations and Suggestions

In light of the increasing importance of cybersecurity, its serious threats and related issues at the international level, awareness of cybersecurity has become extremely important and a pivotal role in preserving ourselves, our families, our society and our countries. African higher education institutions cannot remain passive; they

should promote a culture of cybersecurity among their students, they should raise cybersecurity awareness across the country, through launching of a youth-focused cybersecurity campaign, they have the obligation to protect them and their families and society and to create the conditions for educating our future leaders, by including cybersecurity awareness courses in undergraduate academic programs.

African governments should be convinced that there is a need for each African country to cooperate and share information, and to develop a comprehensive legislation and a proactive approach to meet these challenges and risks, as well as strengthening awareness and education mechanisms, to stop everything that threatens the safety of their societies.

There should be cooperation between Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), telecommunication companies, civil society organizations and higher education institutions in the African countries in order to increase cybersecurity awareness among students by providing educational resources on a regular basis using appropriate communication mediums.

A unit or centre was established for the professional development of faculty members in many higher education institutions. It is recommended that these centres provide awareness training courses on cybersecurity. This training is vital for development in this field, and it should be an integral part of the ongoing professional development of faculty members and employees. Sure, achieving this goal will reduce the number of people who are exposed to the threats of cyber-crime in African states.

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